

ON THE ISSUE OF THE MAIN SOURCES OF THE EMERGENCE AND REPLENISHMENT OF THE VOCABULARY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE THROUGH BORROWINGS

Mammadli M.

*Azerbaijan University of Languages
Lecturer*

Abstract

The article presented for discussion addresses an interesting topic. In modern cognitive linguistics, there are currently numerous scholarly works directly devoted to expanding the English lexicology, but among these, borrowing is the most popular and productive. This aspect is the author's primary focus. However, we believe the author has chosen the right approach in distributing the informational material. Specifically, at the very beginning of the article, in full accordance with the title, a brief but necessary introduction is provided, directing professional linguists and lay readers alike to the history of the subject. This is appropriate, as many words and expressions borrowed into English date back to ancient times. From here, a thread extends to the Indo-European language family, to Latin, and to the Celtic tribe, and then a smooth transition follows to a more modern period. The article should be commended for providing a classification of borrowings that is both convenient and clear, both for linguistic analysis and for perception.

Keywords: borrowing methods, modern English, lexicology, vocabulary development, primary sources, etymology, Anglo-Saxon, Latin.

The origins of individual words and expressions is a key area of modern cognitive linguistics. Azerbaijani and foreign linguists-scholars studying this topic study their etymology, attempting, where possible, to trace not only the original source but also the main stages of their incorporation into a given language. Furthermore, various approaches are used to explore both "their original structure and the most significant lexical-semantic connections" [3, p.296]. Borrowing is one effective way to expand vocabulary. A brief examination of this process using English as an example is the central goal of this article.

First, we consider it necessary to clearly define the group affiliation of the English language. As is well known, it belongs to the Romano-Germanic group, which, in turn, is a branch of the Indo-European family. It turns out that the most ancient words or expressions (including individual historicisms or archaisms) in modern English have Indo-European roots. Given the advanced level of linguistic development in our time and summarizing the opinions of some scholars, we can categorize them. For example, G.N. Babich offers the following classification of borrowed words:

- A). Family and marriage; family relationships: brother, sister, daughter, father, mother;
- B). Factors of action or deed: to come, to know, to sit; to lead;
- C). Quality, characteristic of something: quick, right, sad;
- D). Parts of the body or face: ear, eye, foot;
- E). Flora and fauna: cat, tree, wolf;
- F). Numerals: hundred, ten, three [1, p.9].

We'd like to point out at the very beginning of our article that we've presented one of the most simplified classifications of loanwords. It's simple in its internal structure and, in our opinion, quite clear and illustrative. But this also constitutes its distinct advantage; as we can see, it encompasses a wide variety of areas or spheres of social life.

We also consider it necessary to emphasize that the English language's vocabulary has been actively expanding throughout its centuries-long history. Thus,

by the mid-2020s, attentive and somewhat meticulous linguists calculated that approximately 82 percent of English loanwords and expressions are conditioned by the characterological conditions and circumstances surrounding the development and refinement of the entire language system [1].

Borrowing in this language has proven to be a productive method. This is understandable: firstly, the sources (roots) can be very diverse. Secondly, it involves the transfer of individual components from a second, non-native language, such as words, phrases, phonemes, and morphemes. Moreover, the borrowing process itself occurs as a result of "cultural connections and linguistic contacts" [2, p.178]. It's significant that the English language organically absorbed some loanwords simultaneously with modifications to lexical, semantic, stylistic, syntactic, grammatical, and orthographic norms, adapting them to its own standards. Consequently, the paradigm of English loanwords also shifted.

It's reasonable to ask: if the borrowing we're looking for lasted for centuries, then what exactly was it connected to? This leads us to the interesting fact that borrowings occurred concurrently with certain significant events. Historians are joining the research of linguists. In particular, it turns out that Britain, even in the Early Middle Ages, was repeatedly invaded by various tribes and peoples. Initially (approximately from the mid-7th century BC), the British Isles were inhabited by Celts and Britons, who, in turn, absorbed some elements from the Indo-European family of peoples. Then, more than seven centuries later, that is, by the new era, Britain was again subjected to invasions by tribes that, from 55 BC onwards, had been attacked by the Roman (Ancient) Empire.

Modern historians, together with linguists, have easily discovered that Latin was incorporated into the English language of that distant time, since the ancient Greeks during the period of classical Hellenism spoke and wrote in their native Greek (now Ancient Greek), but the Romans spoke and wrote exclusively in Latin. Hence the influence of the Latins and the Celts. It has

been established that a certain portion of borrowings into English “was completed only in the fifth century of the new era” [7].

Without delving too deeply into history, it’s worth noting that from this period (the 5th century), Britain was repeatedly conquered by Germans, Saxons, Jutes, and Spaniards. This diverse mix of tribes inevitably affected the linguistic aspect of the issue we’re analyzing. Specifically, most of the tribes that attacked Britain spoke a mixture of Spanish and German (or, to be precise, Old High German). Elements of Old English were interbred with Anglo-Saxon, and the process of borrowing began immediately [5].

Let’s give some specific examples. From Anglo-Saxon, English adopted the word “naked”, which comes from the Anglo-Saxon “nacod” (naked, bare) and means obvious, open, or accessible. “To ring”, from the Anglo-Saxon “hring-gan” (to ring, to collide), means (to ring or to sound) in Modern English. Let’s note a curious contamination of loanwords. In the first example, the English word acquired an extremely distant meaning compared to the Anglo-Saxon one; in the second, by contrast, linguists are dealing with near-synonymous concepts.

Furthermore, a similar phenomenon is observed with the lexeme “spade”, which from Anglo-Saxon means “spædu” and translates as “shovel”. English adopted this word with the same meaning, but with the addition of “spade”. The latter is synonymous with “crowbar” which was not intended in the Anglo-Saxon dialect. Then there’s the Anglo-Saxon “tún”, which denotes words such as fence, outskirts, estate, and small town. This word migrated into English “town” “with the generally accepted concept of city” [1, p.14].

Unfortunately, the aforementioned scholar G.N. Babich stops at the last borrowing. However, in our opinion, his thought can and should be successfully expanded. “Town” in modern English has, since ancient times, truly meant a city without any unnecessary specification of its spatio-temporal paradigm. If modern English speakers want to indicate a city’s size, they simply add “small” or “large”, respectively. Meanwhile, the Anglo-Saxon original provides only an elliptical form of the lexeme.

Clearly, a city outskirts or an estate is always smaller than a single large city. Thus, with borrowing, a peculiar transition occurs from “litotes” to “hyperbole”. We have deliberately placed these words in quotation marks because they should be interpreted exclusively figuratively.

Instructive are those loanwords that entered modern English from Latin, but were used not by the Saxons, Spaniards, Jutes, or Normans, but exclusively by the Celts. This population belongs to a distinct branch of the British Isles. And the time is closer to our own. For example, one of the names for food in the Celtic dialect of Latin sounds like “būtyrum cāseus”; it was borrowed into English with this phonetic sound: “Butter Cheese”. A trade term is “Uncia Pondō” - an Inch Pound, respectively. From the world of flora, “Caulis Planta” is a white cabbage (“Ynce pund”), etc.

It’s striking that, regardless of its field of use, borrowings in English have undergone some orthographic

and phonetic changes. However, upon closer examination, it’s clear that their lexical and semantic content has remained essentially the same. We are confident that today’s native English speakers will understand the double phonetic consonance perfectly. However, the reverse process is also observed, where the changes are so significant that they affect both spelling and semantics [6].

For example, the Anglo-Saxon “myln”, derived from the Latin “molina”, means only “mill”. “Mill”, on the other hand, primarily means “flour mill”. At first glance, it might seem that there’s no discernible difference between these terms. In fact, mills have existed among all civilized peoples and nations since ancient times. “Flour mill” in Great Britain (as in many other countries) only appeared in the second half of the 19th century. Therefore, it’s a more modern linguistic innovation. This example demonstrates that borrowings refer to different time periods, and quite distant ones at that.

There are borrowings in which a known correspondence occurs along the lines of a specific material. Thus, the lexeme “street” was borrowed from the Anglo-Saxon word “stræt” (which, incidentally, is extremely close to modern English in its phonetic sound). But the path from the original source to the second language, as they say, is a long one.

In Anglo-Saxon, this word denotes an object that extends into the distance; incidentally, it also implies the presence of a certain layer of material. In modern perception, this would be an asphalt road. The original source does not specify a street; it could refer to any space, whereas when borrowed into English, this word denotes only a “street”, without any deviations, that is, deviations from the semantic norm.

A similar case is observed in the borrowing of the Anglo-Saxon “weall” into English, which has two variants: A) A fortified structure in the form of a rampart; B) Defense against an enemy. In Latin, this word is “vallus” (fence, palisade, hedge). In modern English, it’s “wall”; the phonetic similarity is quite obvious, as is the difference in semantics.

Besides Latin and Germanic borrowings, the English language was significantly enriched by borrowings from Old Norse. As in the previous cases we’ve described, the Scandinavians, who had settled in Sweden, Norway, and neighboring Denmark, also frequently invaded parts of the British Isles. Since the Scandinavian peoples also belonged to the Anglo-Saxon branch, some linguistic elements were nearly identical. Mixed components were generally few. However, the direct influence of the Old Norse on English was significant. Moreover, the borrowing process proceeded at an accelerated pace due to the close relationship of the two languages, or at least their individual branches.

In one of her articles, Elena Kuritskaya insightfully notes that “the cultural element was mixed with the purely linguistic element, namely, borrowing into English occurred systematically and on a massive scale due to facilitated mutual understanding and interaction between people” [4, p.49]. The same scholar cites the following statistics: in modern English, there are currently over eight hundred and eighty words and expressions borrowed from Old Norse. For convenience and

clarity, we will provide a chain of three rows of borrowings: Anglo-Saxon - Old Norse - Modern English.

Thus, from the Anglo-Saxon “blōma”, which means the weight of a certain type of metal and at the same time the Old Norse “blómi” - “flower” - English “bloom” with the same meaning. Let us note how the meanings differ in Anglo-Saxon and Old Norse; The first, as can be seen, is completely unmotivated, while the second is practically identical to the English word. However, such discrepancies are not always observed in borrowings. For example, in Anglo-Saxon, “eorl” is an indicator of a person’s belonging to a higher caste, noble ancestry, and also a courageous warrior. In Old Norse, “jarl” is a king’s subject or viceroy. From these two languages, “earl” - a renowned warrior of earl descent - came into modern English at relatively similar times.

Now let’s decide which of the two borrowed meanings is closest to the original English. Of course, the first is the Anglo-Saxon one, which is associated with a person’s high birth. As for the Old Norse, it most likely denotes a position under the king, rather than a person’s status, much less a person’s character. Thus, it is easy to conclude that the connection between borrowed words and specific motivations can be more or less close. This vaguely resembles the motivation behind phraseological units.

We notice a similar phenomenon in the borrowing of the modern English word “plough”. It is entirely identical to the Old Norse “plógr”, but has the additional meaning of “arable land” or “plowed field” in Anglo-Saxon. In turn, a complete match of meanings is found in the English word “sister”. The Anglo-Saxon “sweostor” and “systir” are Old Norse.

We would like to conclude this article by presenting facts about the borrowing of elements of the Norman language by the English. Here, too, we cannot do without a brief historical commentary. The essence of the matter is that the majority of the Norman population during the aforementioned years spoke a motley mixture of Anglo-Saxon, Old High German, Old English, Latin, and, finally, French.

It is not surprising that, from such a multi-layered mixture of different languages, English began to borrow certain words and expressions. Meanwhile, modern scholars (M.M. Makovsky, Zh.N. Sarangeeva, L.V. Darzhinova, E.V. Kuritskaya, N.S. Novolodskaya, and others) have managed to prove that most of these borrowings came from French. In fact, it turned out that it was precisely this language that the Normans spoke most often.

The question inevitably arises: this language is noticeably distant from the branches that formed the basis of Latin, Anglo-Saxon, Old High German, and Old Norse. It turns out that over the course of several centuries, French seamlessly merged into what is known as Middle English. In particular, it has been discovered that William Shakespeare wrote in it. Many words from the great playwright’s lexicon are difficult for modern translators to decipher. However, as strange as it may sound, it was precisely this language, several centuries

later, that became the ancestor of the modern English literary language.

The scholars we mentioned have established with certainty that by the 19th and 20th centuries, bypassing the late Renaissance, New English (from the Middle English “aiden”, meaning “providing emergency aid”) incorporated lexemes such as “to aid”, with the same basic meaning - to help, to assist, with the complement: “to assist someone”. At the same time, the word “to help” was adopted into English from the Old French “aider”, which had the same meaning (to help, to assist), and from the identical Latin “adiutare”. The New English “beast”, meaning “beast” or “animal” in general, and figuratively “rude”, was also borrowed from both the Middle English “beste” and the Old French “beste”, with virtually the same phonetic pronunciation. Similarly, the modern English “feeble” is borrowed from the Middle English “feble” (meaning feeble, thin, or frail), and from the Old French “foible” (a pitiful person, deplorable), and even from the Latin “flebilis”, with an identical meaning. Examples could be multiplied if desired, but that would be beyond the scope of this article.

So, let’s summarize briefly. In this paper, we have attempted to highlight characteristic examples of the use of loanwords in English across different eras. A brief historical overview prefaces the article to help identify the primary sources that served as the basis for the adoption of certain lexemes or expressions into English. To provide visual evidence, a comparative analysis of some loanwords from different language groups has been provided. These include Middle English, Latin, Anglo-Saxon, Scandinavian French, and several others.

References

1. Бабич Г. Н. *Lexicology: A Current Guide. Лексикология английского языка: учеб. пособие.* Изд-е 6-е, стереотип. М.: Флинта; Наука, 2012. 200 с.
2. *Большая Российская энциклопедия: в 30-ти т. / науч.-ред. совет: Ю. С. Осипов и др. М.: Большая Российская энциклопедия, 2008. Т. 10. Железное дерево – Излучение.* 767 с.
3. *Большая советская энциклопедия: в 30-ти т. / гл. ред. А. М. Прохоров. Изд-е 3-е. М.: Советская энциклопедия, 1978. Т. 30. Эклибрис,* 632 с.
4. Курицкая Е. В. *Этимология заимствований в современном английском языке // Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики.* 2019, Том 12, выпуск № 3, с. 47-52.
5. *Longman Dictionary of English Language and Culture. 3rd revised edition.* Harlow: Pearson Education, Ltd., 2005. 1680 p.
6. Skeat W. W. *The Concise Dictionary of English Etymology.* Ware: Wordsworth Editions, Ltd., 1994. 633 p.
7. *The Oxford Dictionary of English Etymology / ed. by C. T. Onions.* Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1966. 1042 p.